

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B407
 Date: 17 Oct 08
 Take Off: 10:03:42
 Landing: 14:27:26
 Flight Time 4h 22m 44s

Campaign: VOCALS UK test flight

Operating Area: East Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
7	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / Buck / FTP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
11	Wet Neph / PSAP / CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
12	MARSS / DEIMOS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
13	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
14	AMS / SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
15	CAPS / 2D	James Dorsey	Manchester University	
16	VACC	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University	
17	VACC training	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
18	SAW	Ray Freshwater	Cambridge University	
19	camera	Coskun Halil	Skyworks	
20	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	

Flight Track:

B407 Track 17-OCT-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B407
 Date: 17 Oct 2008
 Project: VOCALS (predet test)
 Location: Off East Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095625		ASP	0.14 kft	196	open
100342		T/O	0.13 kft	212	Cranfield
101530	102807	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.29 kft	054	
101730		nev	9.2 kft	039	zero
102039		JW	5.8 kft	039	zero
102606		Temp	1.8 kft	040	DI & NDI temps tracking ok
102807	112511	Run 1	0.29 - 0.43 kft	330	
102907		bbr	0.34 kft	332	retract
102948		GE	0.33 kft	332	ok
103106		Heimann	0.34 kft	331	cal 7
103121		TWC	0.37 kft	331	status good
103323		HORACE	0.33 kft	335	recording
104751		Satcom C	0.39 kft	318	sending ok, RX ok
104820		ISDN	0.39 kft	316	connection ok
112511	113026	Profile 2	0.43 - 6.0 kft	128	
112831		rad alt	4.2 kft	127	ok
113026	114303	Run 2	6.0 kft	127	
113417		bbr	6.0 kft	086	upper drs counts good
113437		bbr	6.0 kft	085	lower drs counts good
113639		nev	6.0 kft	085	zero cal
114304	114759	Profile 3	6.0 - 6.9 kft	358	
114557		turb probe	6.9 kft	013	derived data ok
114759	114825	Run 3	6.9 - 6.8 kft	010	
114826	115012	Profile 4	6.8 - 5.5 kft	010	
115013	115210	Run 4	5.5 - 5.4 kft	326	
115210	115238	Profile 5	5.4 - 5.0 kft	156	
115239	120240	Run 5.1	5.0 - 4.8 kft	156	
120424	121425	Run 5.2	4.9 kft	296	
121425	122021	Profile 6	4.8 - 10.0 kft	324	
122021	123018	Run 6	10.0 kft	162	
123018	123926	Profile 7	10.0 - 17.9 kft	153	
123939	125138	Run 7	18.0 kft	262	
125155	131019	Profile 8	17.7 - 0.42 kft	315	
131033	140129	Run 8	0.44 kft	179	
140144	141544	Profile 9	0.59 - 7.6 kft	158	(! end marked late)
141445		Heimann	9.1 kft	240	cal 07
142726		Land	0.18 kft	214	Cranfield
142921		ASP	0.19 kft	320	closed

B407 Track 17-OCT-08

Sortie Flight B407
17th October 2008.
VOCALS Test Flight

Mission Scientist: Grant Allen, Uni. Manchester

Outline Schedule (Local time):

07:00 Power to aircraft – Warm-up
09:00 Briefing
10:15 Clear Aircraft and Security check
10:30 Doors close
11:00 Takeoff from Cranfield
15:00 Land at Cranfield
15:30 Debrief
16:00 Power Down

Aims:

To test the qualitative performance of all instrumentation prior to transit from Cranfield to Arica, Chile, in support of the VOCALS field campaign. Data is required both in and out of cloud (both warm and ice-phase if possible) at a range of altitudes from within the boundary layer and well into the free troposphere. In-cloud measurements and low-level aerosol measurements over sea will be made.

Location:

Transit along the East Coast from Cranfield to area of operations in the North Sea off the East Coast of Edinburgh.

Sortie Summary:

After a high level transit to The Wash, low-level aerosol and plume measurements will be made over sea at 500 ft during the transit to our area of in-cloud operations off the East Coast of Scotland. In-cloud ops will consist of several 10-minute straight and level North-South oriented runs at increasing altitude within boundary layer and ice cloud (if present), followed by an out of cloud run at 20000 ft. Reciprocal return to Cranfield.

Weather:

Thick developing boundary layer Sc and Ci expected in the morning NE of the Humber over the North Sea, thinning throughout the day in a south-eastward-moving, weakening warm front. Clear sky conditions expected over England and the SE. High pressure building throughout. Light northwesterly winds. High pressure and low winds likely to cap pollution plumes and limit cloud development south of the warm front.

Way points

ALPHA = 56 N, 1° 10 W (Ampep WP76)

BRAVO = 55° 30 N, 1° 10 W

Note that ALPHA and BRAVO should be in an area of boundary layer cloud; if necessary these points can be repositioned

Ampep points: 87, 80, 79, 77, 76

Sortie Detail with approximate timings:

1. Take off and transit at cruising altitude of 11000 ft to Ampep WP87 (The Wash), descending over sea to arrive at 500 ft (T+20m)
2. Transit north at 500 ft along the East Coast between WP87, WP80, WP79, WP77 and WP76 (T+1h 20m)
3. Ascend to fly within boundary layer cloud and fly 10-minute straight and level run between ALPHA and BRAVO (T+1h 30m)
4. Reciprocal run at same altitude between BRAVO and ALPHA (T+1h 40m)
5. Ascend in increments of 1000 ft (and staying within cloud) and fly 4 straight and level runs between ALPHA and BRAVO, ascending at the end of run. Reduce altitude increments to remain in cloud if necessary. (T+ 2h 20m)
6. 180-degree turning ascent to 10000 ft or altitude of high (ice) cloud if present. Straight and level run at 10000 ft (or within ice cloud) between ALPHA and BRAVO and reciprocate at same altitude (T+ 2h 30m)
7. 180-degree turning ascent to 20000 ft in clear air with straight and level run between ALPHA and BRAVO (T+2h40)
8. Profile descent to 500 ft and recovery to Cranfield along reciprocal route (WP76, WP77, WP79, WP80, WP87) with transit from The Wash to Cranfield at 11000 ft. (T+4h)

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – nadir during high level runs to characterise clouds. Zenith during below cloud runs.

ARIES – nadir viewing throughout

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Miss Scientist Notes:

Aim is to measure in-cloud as much as possible with some profiling and aerosol sampling in the boundary layer up to the free troposphere.

Information:

At 11Z on 17/10/2008, from 03Z on 16/10/2008
Cloud cover and PMSL Operational uk4

- High > 50%
- Med > 50%
- Low > 50%
- Stratus > 10%
- Fog > 40%

Mission Scientist's Debrief

Flight No : B407 Date : 17/10/08 Name: GRANT ALLEN

1. Assessment of the flight

Core objectives were met - aerosol plumes, in-cloud runs and clear-air legs were measured. Weakening warm front and resulting dissipating cloud required a deviation to the West from WP77 to sample necessary cloud.

Aerosol plumes from the Humber etc. were sampled at 500 ft low-level outward and return legs. CO, SO₂, NO_x, O₃, and aerosol showed fresh plume character.

Cloud ops were made between 6 and 15000 ft. Multiple cloud layers, intermittent, mixed phase & ice cloud sampled. Some thick cloud was sampled on 8000 ft run, but mostly thin and intermittent.

2. Summary of the weather conditions

Cloud free out to the sea. Mid-level cloud thickened on Northward transit. The warm front we hoped would yield significant cloud did not, hence deviation out to the west on arrival at Scottish border.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B407** Date 17/10/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30	/	0			WEATHER at CRAWFIELD:
					Sunny, clear sky. Low humidity, v. light
					Swesterly Winds.
					- James Dorsey reporting UHSAS
					failure.
11:00	-			CRAWFIELD.	T/O
11:10					1st invasion Cap at 5000 ft -
					stable above.
11:20					Start of transit - 5000ft -
					WP86.
					Slight increase in SO ₂ (0.5pphr)
					Coincides with decrease in O ₂
					and CO increase.
11:40					CO cal. Ignore spike.
					Mid-level cloud. No low-level
					cloud yet.
11:47					WP80 reached.
12:00					Mid-level SC thickening
					and lowering. E of Newcastle.
12:05					Entering Flumber plume
12:15					Change of flight plan to head
					W into cloud from WP77.
12:20					SMAS problem. AMS.
12:25					Ascending

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B407** Date **17/10/08** Name **G.ALLEN** Page **2** of

LOCAL GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					VACC registering good.
12:25					Start of profile climb into cloud
12:30					Entering cloud. Thin and intermittent. 10 min S&L run.
12:42					Run 3 into ice cloud at 8000 ft.
12:50					Turn and descend to catch thicker cloud layer. 10 min S&L followed by reciprocal path. Some thick cloud sampled. 20-5 CAPS reporting good data.
13:00					Reciprocal run started. Not as much cloud on the reciprocal run.
13:02					MS2 reports all cloud probes performing normally.
13:14					Profile 6 to 10000 ft.
13:30					Profile climb to 20000 ft.
13:55					CV1 concerned about Butanol fumes in the inlet affecting
14:15					Several strong plumes on 500 ft return. CO > 220 ppbv SO ₂ and ¹⁰ ppb anti-correlated and correlated with NO _x .

Instruments

Core Chem: All ok.

Comms: Prob with satcom C.

SP-2 - Worked nominally - look at data.

Neph - Working fine.

CVI: Suspected high Butand on CVI inlet.
Paul W to check with AMS

Buck - Working fine.

CAPS / 205: All ok. T & RH suspicion on CAPS.

UHSAS: * Not working - return to DMT.

SAW Hygrometer: Working fine - good test data.

CLOUD PHYSICS: CIP-15 alignment problems. All else functioning well. New COP well behaved.

MARS: Fine.

PREASP: All fine.

CPC on CCN rack - Flooded. One column on CCN problem.

PSAP: Check flows! Jamie Treloar to check data.

PAN: Working well.

VACC: All fine.

SUS/ARIES: SWS & SHIMS working fine.
Lower Shims fine Aries fine.

AMS: All ok. Stopped logging for 15 mins. CPD has inbound led. SWS not used.

Mission Scientist's Log 2

Flight No B. 107

Date 17/10/08

Name Phil Brown

Page 1 of 2

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
100342					T/O
101530					Start P1
105039					increase in PCASP - not CO
105306					PCASP rise - small incr. in CO
/					Start of Teeside plume?
105824					CO rising also PCASP.
/					Teeside plume
/					SO ₂ +ve response in this plume
110005					Good data for AofA cal on this leg & nice and steady.
/					End R1 at point 77
112338					
112512					Start P2
1146					Two Nevz look OK in thin patchy cloud.
115013					Start R4
/					Nevz. peaks ~ 0.6 gm ⁻³
/					hotwires on CIP ~ 1.1
115841					2DC, CAPS, 2DS all seeing ice precip from above, T = -1.5
120000					more good LWC peaks.
/					Nevz Two picking up the ice precip ok
/					
120240					End R5
1214					Good LWC peak, CIP

narrow spectrum at end.

121425

end R6

Chemistry Log

Date: 17/10/08

Flight: B807

Operator: RT

Preflight

SO₂ on too

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">1.0</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">7.0</div>
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	
Flows			
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">N.I.O NOx</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	
Other			
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
TDLAS			
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 230V	230V power breakers on	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laptop	On and software working	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data	Being saved to correct directories	

Post Flight

Switch off			
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO	Switch off instrument	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	
Driers			
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Small drier	Change if spent	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data transfer	To memory stick	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laptop	Shut down	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"></div>
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

BA07

In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	
09:36	Ground	94.30	339	31967	37.21	7.50	
09:58	Post post transfer	94.82	334	31668	37.69	7.50	
10:43	500FT.	92.66	334	30975	38.02	7.52	23.36,
11:33	FL060	93.62	331	30951	36.99	7.50	23.45
12:05	FL050	94.04	329	30930	37.08	7.50	23.33
12:49	FL080	93.92	330	31029	37.60	7.53	23.40
13:14	500FT	92.98	329	30627	38.07	7.53	23.45
13:43	500FT	92.96	331	30762	37.85	7.51	23.44
14:30	Ground.	92.96	333	30958	37.86	7.50	23.40.
In flight comments							
<p>11:24 CO cal aborted for profile Hugh requests manual cals during VOZALS</p>							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 407

Date: 17/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:15:07	95	0.09	7													Start Profile 1 from FL110	
10:16:08	85	0.09														FL100	
10:17:10	80	0.09														FL090	
10:18:44	100	0.10														FL080	
10:19:15	140	0.09														FL070	
10:20:08	170	0.09														FL060	
10:21:15	160	0.09														FL050	
10:22:20	130	0.09														FL040	
10:23:50	55	0.09														FL030	
10:25:00	110	0.09														FL020	
10:26:35	670	0.09														FL010	
10:27:38	700	0.09														End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ 500'	
10:28:00	650	0.09	8														
10:30:00	680	0.09															
10:32:00	900	0.08	9														
10:34:00	900	0.08	10														
10:36:00	400	0.08															
10:38:00	400	0.08															
10:40:00	300	0.08	11														
10:42:00	230	0.09	12														
10:44:00	250	0.09															
10:46:00	250	0.09															
10:48:00	300	0.09															
10:50:00	700	0.09	13														
10:52:00	850	0.09	14														
10:54:00	230	0.09															
10:56:00	300	0.09	15														
10:58:00	680	0.08															
11:00:00	1600	0.08															
11:02:00	600	0.08	16														
11:04:00	340	0.08															
11:06:00	515	0.08															
11:08:00	450	0.08	17														
11:10:00	410	0.09															
11:12:00	230	0.09	18														
11:14:00	100	0.09															
11:16:00	200	0.09	19														
11:18:00	160	0.10															
11:20:00	135	0.09															
11:20:35																End of Run	
11:24:45	210	0.09	20													Start Profile 2 from 500'	
11:25:25	90	0.09														FL010	
11:26:23	45	0.09														FL020	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.35	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 407

Date: 17/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:27:11	30	0.09	20													FL030	
11:28:05	20	0.09														FL040	
11:28:58	900	0.19	31			10										FL050	
11:29:48																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ FL060	
11:30:00	40	0.08															
11:32:00	25	0.09	40			8	100								10		
11:34:00	25	0.09															
11:36:00	11	0.08															
11:38:00	140	0.09				3	800								8		
11:40:00	115	0.10	41			2	800								8		
11:42:00	110	0.10															
11:42:37																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 3 from FL060	
11:43:47																End of P3 & Start Run 3 @ FL070	
11:44:00	40	0.09	58			1											
11:46:00	45	0.09	63														
11:47:00																End of Run & Start Profile 4	
11:49:30	85	0.08														FL060	
11:49:47																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 4 @ FL055	
11:50:00	85	0.09															
11:51:37																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 5	
11:52:14																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 5 @ FL048	
11:53:00	480	0.10	190			10	100								12		
11:55:00	100	0.09	193														
11:57:00	130	0.10	198			4	800								8		
11:59:00	100	0.30	267			100	600								8		
12:01:00	50	0.11	286			15	800								8		
12:02:20																End of Run 5 (CDP heater)	
12:04:02																Start Run 6 @ FL048	
12:05:00	70	0.11	307			5	800								12		
12:07:00	280	0.17	314			100	450								1		
12:09:00	170	0.09	336														
12:11:00	45	0.10															
12:13:00	420	0.34	407			8	100								12		
12:14:03																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 6	
12:15:20	100	0.09	482													FL060	
12:16:14	45	0.09				1										FL070	
12:17:27	15	0.08				1										FL080	
12:18:46	6	0.07														FL090	
12:19:46																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 7 @ FL100	
12:20:00	50	0.07	497														
12:22:00	35	0.07															
12:24:00	50	0.17	520														
12:26:00	35	0.08	521			1	800								8		

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.35	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 407

Date: 17/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:28:00	30	0.10	568			5	800								12		
12:29:50																End of Run 7 & Start Profile 7	
12:31:25	25	0.08	650			1	800								12	FL110	
12:32:40	25	0.11	655			1	800								12	FL120	
12:33:41	25	0.12	657			8	800								12	FL130	
12:34:49	20	0.08														FL140	
12:35:50	35	0.08														FL150	
12:36:55	35	0.07														FL160	
12:37:52	30	0.07														FL170	
12:39:09																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 8 @ FL180	
12:40:00	40	0.07				1	400								8		
12:42:00	35	0.07				1											
12:44:00	60	0.17	659			2	800								8		
12:46:00	70	0.14	662			9	800								8		
12:48:00	50	0.09	671			25	500								8		
12:50:00	150	0.17	672			10	800								8		
12:51:11																End of Run 8 & Start Profile 8 from FL180	
12:52:26	90	0.09	673			12	700								8	FL170	
12:53:00	95	0.08	674			1										FL160	
12:54:04	80	0.12				2										FL150	
12:55:06	75	0.08				1	600								8	FL140	
12:56:15	25	0.08														FL130	
12:57:20	25	0.07														FL120	
12:58:17	45	0.07														FL110	
12:59:17	15	0.07	676													FL100	
13:00:48	85	0.13	688													FL090	
13:01:30	100	0.09														FL080	
13:02:37	65	0.09														FL070	
13:03:39	15	0.08														FL060	
13:04:36																FL050	
13:05:46	25	0.08														FL040	
13:06:49	60	0.10														FL030	
13:07:48	95	0.10	689													FL020	
13:08:54	170	0.10														FL010	
13:09:58																End of Profile & Start Run 9 @ 500'	
13:10:00	150	0.09															
13:12:00	280	0.09	690														
13:14:00	300	0.09															
13:16:00	310	0.09															
13:18:00	400	0.09															
13:20:00	1200	0.08	691														
13:22:00	530	0.09															
13:24:00	560	0.09															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.35	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.5CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 407

page 1 of 2

Date: 17/Oct/2008 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NORTH SEA

Scans: either "[IGMS]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
07 27	—	Power up OK					NOTE: Year in data files is 2000 !!!
07 29			CH	C	57	38	
07 44 35		1x60	C	C	51	30	
07 45 20		1x60	H	C	51	30	
08 24 18			N	O	51	24	Script NadirLongRun3min (incl. low in CH)
08 30			Z	O	51	23	Script ZenithLongRun3min Clear above. Thin Ci?
09 37	—						Stopped script at ~09 37.
~10 00	TAKE OFF						
10 27 38	↓ 500ft	360 x 1 NLR3min	N	C	51	19	NadirLongRun3min
	SLR.						Clear above Broken Cu nearby
10 34							Stratosomething overhead?
10 36							CSS @ 19.08°C MCT ~ 285k low ~ 290k?
10 50					51	20	MCT = 319k H88
11 55							☁ Cloud above
11 07					51	20	MCT = 280k (should be ~ 324k?)
11 21					51	21	Stopped script while banking
11 23 17	500ft.	Script NLR3min	N	C	51	21	Script NadirLongRun3min
11 24 30	↑						More banking. End 11 25 20.
11 30 13	F2060	Script NLR3min	N	C	51	21	Script NadirLongRun3min
							In cloud base (occasionally out)
					51	21	MCT = 320k
11 43 04	↑						End of script
11 44 20		NLR3min	N	C			Script NadirLongRun3min
11 48	↓						End script
11 50 19	SLR.	NLR3min	N	C	51	17	Script NLR3min
11 55	—						Acquisition stalled at "357/360 runs"
11 56 30		NLR3min			51	15	Script NadirLongRun3min
12 02	FL		N	C	51	14.5	End of script
12 10 26		NLR3min	N	C	51	14	Script NadirLongRun3min
12 14 30					51	13	End of script

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	17/10/08	Flight	B407	log pages
Operator(s)	JNB	Campaign	VOCALS test flight		
Departure	Arrival				

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	Still there				•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	Yup				•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	Yup				•	
FERA on			at time	0905		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating					•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•	
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time			
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers					
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip		
	Surface		Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	
Brightness temps 'sensible'				•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)
				Ch20
				(44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight #	B	Date		Operator(s)		log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
1024			In profile descent passing through Sc5 below Ci1.						
			Initial problems caused by black knob on MARSS CPU in in-correct position. Took me a while to notice as it's not usually touched. Checked all connections though whilst trying to resolve issue. So sorry for the lack of start up data. Got overlooked in the rush. As did setting the time on the MARSS pc.						
1026			Over sea.						
102807	1	FL005	2/8 SC5 6/8 AC3 1/8 Ci1						
1039	1	FL005	Now below 4/8 sc5 unsure what else is up there						
1048	1	FL005	Cloud now 6/8 AC3						
1056	1	FL005	7/8 SC5						
1104	1	FL005	Passing point 79						
			Below 8/8 sc5						
1120	1	FL005	Passing point 77						
			Cloud appears to be ac rather than sc now. Still a good 7/8						
112511	1	FL005	End of run – start of profile 2 ascent						
1129	P2	FL060	Into sc5						
113026	2	FL060	Start of run 2						
114304	P3		Start of profile 3 ascent						
114826	P4		End of profile 3 start of profile 4 descent						
115030	4	FL075	End of profile descent – start of run 4						
115210	P5	FL050	End of run followed by short profile descent (of 500 ft) and start of run 5 at 7000ft						
	5.1		Still in cloud.						
	5.1		Flying partly between layers and partly in cloud.						
120424	5.2	FL049	End of run 5 start of run 5.2						
			Still in intermittent layer cloud						
121445	P6		End of run start of profile ascent						
122021	6	FL100	End of profile 6 start of run 6. Between cloud layers but with intermittent patches.						
123018	P7		End of run 6 start of profile 7 ascent 70 FL180						
123939	7	FL180	End of profile climb start of run 7						
			Still in between cloud layers – appears to be 7/8 below AS/SC 6/8 Ci2 above						
125138	P8		End of run 7 start of profile 8 to 500ft						
			Still over North Sea 2/8 sc5 below – 7/8 of multiple layers above consisting of AS CS						
131033	8	FL005	End of profile descent – start of run 8 abeam point 77. 7/8 multilayered cloud above. Nil below.						
1333	8	FL005	No real change in cloud amounts though the lowest layer looks more like 4/8 sc4 with cu1 in between.						
1345	8	FL005	Lower layers now down to 1/8 still a good 5/8 of mid-level cloud though. but certainly thing as we progress South.						

B407_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:17:39.49 --- - - - -
08:17:39.49 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:17:39.49 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:17:39.49 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
08:17:39.49 --- - - - -
08:17:44.56 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:17:45.81 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:17:47.50 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:17:48.76 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:17:50.43 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:17:51.60 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:18:01.96 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:18:02.05 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:18:02.14 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:18:06.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:07.71 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:08.98 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:16.83 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:16.84 SWS - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:20.07 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:20.08 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:23.05 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:23.06 LSH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
08:18:24.53 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:18:29.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:18:29.42 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:18:29.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:18:32.86 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:33.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:33.26 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:18:39.82 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:18:42.41 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:18:51.52 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 110.000
08:18:52.63 SWS 103.3 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:18:59.54 LSH - - - - Idling
08:18:59.69 USH - - - - Idling
08:18:59.79 SWS - - - - Idling
08:29:47.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:29:47.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:29:47.24 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:09.58 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:10.10 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:30:13.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:17.14 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:30:22.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:24.53 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:25.70 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:27.06 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:27.99 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:30.50 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:33.05 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:30:33.05 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:30:36.89 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:30:36.90 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
08:30:38.73 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:40.18 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:41.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:42.71 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:30:48.30 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:30:51.74 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:38.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:40.55 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:41.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:42.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:42.21 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:43.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

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08:31:44.18 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:45.66 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:45.85 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:31:49.31 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:31:49.88 USH - - - - Idling
08:31:49.90 SWS - - - - Idling
08:31:50.15 LSH - - - - Idling
08:34:10.48 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:34:12.49 SWS - - - - Idling
09:26:11.97 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:16.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:16.52 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:19.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:26:21.10 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:26:24.70 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:26:31.61 SWS - - - - Idling
09:26:31.62 USH - - - - Idling
09:26:31.84 LSH - - - - Idling
09:31:57.44 --- - - - - *** pre flight cooler at 14 deg
09:32:04.65 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:04.66 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:04.66 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:08.87 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:32:13.09 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:13.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:13.34 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:14.53 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:14.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:16.94 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:32.91 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:32.94 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:33.01 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:32:34.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:34.56 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:36.75 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:32:37.41 USH - - - - Idling
09:32:37.45 SWS - - - - Idling
09:32:37.60 LSH - - - - Idling
09:32:45.04 --- - - - - *** 13 deg
10:00:18.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:00:18.85 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:00:18.86 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:02:04.28 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:04:36.32 SWS 110.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
10:04:37.46 SWS -2.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
10:05:14.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:05:16.34 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:05:17.50 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:10.45 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:08:13.11 SWS - - - - Idling
10:08:13.13 USH - - - - Idling
10:08:13.89 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:19.96 LSH - - - - Idling
10:08:21.33 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:08:26.41 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:29.08 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:08:30.41 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:09:06.46 --- - - - -
10:09:06.46 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:09:06.46 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:09:06.46 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
10:09:06.46 --- - - - -
10:09:10.43 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:09:12.22 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:09:18.94 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:09:28.44 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:09:28.54 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:09:28.63 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK

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10:09:32.78 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:09:35.45 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:09:35.45 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:09:36.72 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:09:38.57 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:09:38.57 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 300ms.
10:09:39.66 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:09:41.09 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:09:41.10 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:09:43.67 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
10:09:43.67 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
10:09:50.46 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:09:53.66 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:09:53.67 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:09:53.67 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:09:54.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:09:54.99 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:10:01.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:02.87 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:10:02.89 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:10:11.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:10:13.24 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:14:14.98 --- - - - -
10:14:14.98 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:14:14.98 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:14:14.98 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
10:14:14.98 --- - - - -
10:14:17.73 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:14:20.47 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:14:21.42 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:14:23.61 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:14:26.02 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:14:32.44 SWS - - 45 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 45ms.
10:14:34.16 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:14:35.04 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:14:38.10 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:14:38.11 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:14:40.28 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:14:43.09 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:14:43.09 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:14:49.73 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:14:49.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:14:49.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:14:55.22 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:14:56.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:14:57.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:14:58.20 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:14:59.32 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:17:38.48 --- - - - -
10:17:38.48 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:17:38.48 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:17:38.48 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
10:17:38.48 --- - - - -
10:17:41.65 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:17:44.63 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:17:47.60 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:17:52.82 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:17:53.00 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:17:53.09 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:18:02.42 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
10:18:05.01 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
10:18:12.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:18:12.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:18:12.52 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:18:14.07 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:18:15.81 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:18:15.82 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.

```

10:18:17.60	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:18:19.06	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:18:19.06	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:18:20.37	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
10:18:22.03	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:18:22.04	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
10:18:44.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:44.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:18:45.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:47.47	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:19:13.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:19:17.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:17.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:19:18.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:19.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:20.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:21.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:22.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:24.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:24.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:19:25.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:19:28.93	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:22:48.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:48.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:22:49.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:53.22	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:22:56.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:58.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:59.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:22:59.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:23:00.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:01.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:02.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:03.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:05.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:25.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:26.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:50.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:51.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:27.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
10:27:30.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:27:32.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:33.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:27:34.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:50.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:29:51.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:29:52.47	SWS	169.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:29:57.21	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:30:01.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:01.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:01.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:03.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:03.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:03.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:30:03.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:09.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:09.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:09.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:10.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:30:11.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:11.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:11.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:49.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws in nadir while low over sea surface
10:32:07.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:07.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:07.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:09.67	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:32:11.36	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:32:12.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.

10:32:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:15.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:15.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:16.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:16.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:17.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:17.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:17.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:18.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:32:18.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:19.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:19.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:27.10	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
10:32:27.10	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
10:32:29.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:32.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:33.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:33.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:32:34.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:38.17	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 50ms.
10:32:38.17	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 50ms.
10:32:52.90	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
10:32:52.91	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
10:32:56.62	USH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
10:32:56.63	USH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
10:32:59.75	LSH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
10:32:59.75	LSH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
10:33:02.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:02.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:02.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:03.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:03.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:03.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:03.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:05.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:05.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:05.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:05.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:06.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:06.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:06.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:48.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:48.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:48.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:48.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:34:48.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:49.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:49.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:46.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:46.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:46.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:47.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:47.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:47.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:36:47.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:27.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
10:43:32.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:32.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:32.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:33.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:33.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:33.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:34.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:25.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:25.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:25.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:25.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:25.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:25.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

10:46:26.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:28.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:28.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:28.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:28.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:28.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:28.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:29.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:32.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:35.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:36.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:04.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:04.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:47:04.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:06.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:07.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:09.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:36.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:36.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:36.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:36.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:36.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:37.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:48:37.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:40.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:40.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:40.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:40.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:54:41.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:41.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:56.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:56.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:56.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:57.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:57.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:58:57.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:57.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:48.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:48.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:48.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:49.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:49.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:00:49.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:49.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:55.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:55.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:55.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:55.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:00:56.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:56.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:56.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:45.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** waypoint 79
11:04:48.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:48.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:04:49.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:04:49.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:49.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:49.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:49.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:55.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:55.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:55.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:55.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:06:56.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:56.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:56.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:09:01.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:01.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:01.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:01.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:01.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:02.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:02.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:09:02.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:11.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:11:26.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
11:11:41.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:41.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:41.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:41.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:11:42.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:42.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:42.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:47.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:49.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:49.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:11:50.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:26.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:26.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:26.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:27.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:27.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:27.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:38.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:38.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:14:39.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:39.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:39.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:43.78	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:14:47.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:47.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:47.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:14:47.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:47.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:48.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:14:48.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:52.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
11:18:50.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:50.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:50.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:18:50.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:18:51.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:51.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:51.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:23:11.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:24:34.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:25:12.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile climb
11:25:47.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:47.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:47.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:48.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:48.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:48.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:25:48.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:52.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:52.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:52.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:52.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:52.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:53.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:26:53.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:25.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** going into cloud
11:27:58.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg

```

11:29:09.19 --- - - - - *** going into cloud layer now
11:30:18.48 --- - - - - *** run at FL 60
11:31:25.94 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:31:25.98 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:31:26.01 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:31:26.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:31:26.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:31:26.80 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:31:27.10 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:31:27.32 USH - - - - Idling
11:36:01.96 --- - - - -
11:36:01.97 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:36:01.97 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:36:01.97 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
11:36:01.97 --- - - - -
11:36:04.52 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:36:07.10 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:36:09.91 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:36:13.22 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:36:13.31 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:36:13.49 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:36:14.87 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:16.13 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:36:16.48 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:36:16.74 USH - - - - Idling
11:36:17.75 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:23.92 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:36:25.78 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:25.78 SWS - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:26.76 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:36:28.53 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:28.53 USH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:29.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:31.09 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:36:33.42 LSH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:33.43 LSH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:36:34.18 LSH - - - - Idling
11:36:35.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:38.18 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:36:41.72 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:36:42.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:43.50 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:36:43.77 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:36:44.45 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:36:45.14 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:36:46.12 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:37:23.72 --- - - - -
11:37:23.72 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:37:23.72 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:37:23.72 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
11:37:23.72 --- - - - -
11:37:26.75 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:37:29.18 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:37:31.66 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:37:35.49 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:37:35.66 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:37:35.75 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:37:35.76 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:37:36.86 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:37:38.71 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:37:46.31 LSH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:46.32 LSH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:48.87 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:48.87 USH - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:51.47 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:51.47 SWS - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:37:52.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

```

11:37:52.80 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:37:52.80 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:37:55.33 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:37:59.67 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:00.61 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:01.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:01.71 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:38:02.39 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:03.38 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:04.34 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:06.49 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:07.44 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:36.47 SWS - - 20 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:36.48 SWS - - - 20 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:41.47 USH - - 20 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:41.48 USH - - - 20 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:44.33 LSH - - 20 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:44.33 LSH - - - 20 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:38:45.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:45.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:45.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:38:46.15 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:38:46.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:46.83 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:38:47.03 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:39:55.63 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:39:56.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:39:57.55 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:39:57.82 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:39:58.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:39:59.02 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:39:59.66 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:42:42.60 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
11:42:45.88 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:42:52.87 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
11:43:03.79 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
11:43:06.39 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:43:15.22 --- - - - - *** profile 3
11:43:30.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:30.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:30.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:30.91 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:31.11 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:31.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:31.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:31.52 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:33.10 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:43:36.76 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:36.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:36.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:37.39 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:37.45 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:37.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:37.82 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:40.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:40.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:40.78 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:43:41.13 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:41.33 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:41.55 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:43:41.83 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:54:31.47 --- - - - -
11:54:31.47 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:54:31.47 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:54:31.48 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B407
11:54:31.48 --- - - - -
11:54:34.72 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:54:37.78 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.

```

11:54:41.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:54:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:54:41.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:54:59.52	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:55:01.82	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:01.83	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:03.09	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:55:04.90	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:04.90	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:06.52	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:55:08.76	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:08.77	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
11:55:09.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:09.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:09.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:12.99	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:55:17.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:18.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:20.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:20.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:55:21.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:22.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:55:23.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:03.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
11:56:05.84	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:57:10.63	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:10.64	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:12.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:12.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:15.87	USH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:15.88	USH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:19.56	LSH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:19.56	LSH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
11:57:28.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:57:32.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:33.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:57:33.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:33.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
12:00:34.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** LSH still
12:00:46.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** not working
12:00:55.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** USH shutteres still not woring
12:01:32.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:32.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:01:33.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:35.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:01:41.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:41.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:41.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:42.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:01:42.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:42.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:42.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:47.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:47.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:47.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:47.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:01:47.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:48.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:48.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:37.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
12:04:58.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:58.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:58.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:59.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:04:59.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:04:59.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:59.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:00.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:06:11.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:06:17.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:06:23.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:23.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:23.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:06:23.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:06:23.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:24.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:24.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:06:59.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
12:14:28.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:14:37.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
12:15:30.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
12:16:43.04	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:16:43.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:16:47.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:47.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:47.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:47.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:48.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:48.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:16:48.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:48.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:38.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:41.35	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:17:45.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:46.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:47.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:48.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:20:15.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
12:20:43.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
12:30:23.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
12:35:17.17	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:35:22.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:22.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:22.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:22.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:22.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:35:22.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:35:23.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:35:23.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:35:49.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:39:02.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:08.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:08.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:08.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:39:09.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:09.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:39:09.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:09.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:42.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** high level run
12:40:05.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL 180
12:44:22.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:49:47.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
12:55:17.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:55:25.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
12:55:28.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:28.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:28.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:55:28.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:28.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:55:28.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:55:29.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:22.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:22.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:25.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:26.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:57:26.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:28.70	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:57:32.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:57:32.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:32.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:57:32.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:32.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:33.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:33.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:37.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:01:04.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:16:47.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:18:23.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:25:00.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
13:25:03.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:25:06.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:06.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:06.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:06.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:07.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:25:07.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:07.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:09.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:09.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:09.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:25:09.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:10.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:10.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:07.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
13:36:44.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
13:40:12.24	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:40:17.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:18.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:18.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:18.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:18.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:18.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:19.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:24.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:26.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:26.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:26.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:26.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:27.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:40:27.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:46.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
13:43:50.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
13:48:46.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:55:14.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:01:26.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing
14:02:48.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:05:18.30	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:05:23.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:23.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:23.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:24.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:05:24.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:24.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:24.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:28.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:09:34.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:34.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:34.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:34.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:34.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:34.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:34.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:35.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:35.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:39.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:09:39.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:42.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:42.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:42.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:42.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:42.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:42.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:42.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:43.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:50.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:50.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:51.33	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:09:55.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:55.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:55.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:57.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:57.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:57.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:57.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:57.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:58.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:58.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:58.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:13.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science
14:10:24.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:10:43.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:43.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:11:03.64	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 130.000
14:11:04.95	SWS	128.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

B407

①

instrument status.

AMS fine
SMPS not fine. -
Satcom C no power reports.
VACC working OK.
~~SMPS~~

Flight:

B407

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B407

Date: 17/10/08

Instruments

CVI - suspected high butanol on CVI inlet Paul W to check with AMS
PSAP - JT to check flows to determine max alt for flow control. Data not transferred to FM pc, so not processed.

NEPH - ok
SWS - fine
SHIMS - upper ok, lower shims stopped in flight – not yet sorted
AMS - All ok, stopped logging for small intervals
SP2 - working, needs data check, probably good
Core Chem – all good
Cloud physics - CIP15 alignment problems all else functioning well, new CDP well behaved. PCASP fine

CPC on CCN rack - flooded
CCN - one column bad data, to be investigated
FWVS - not run
ARIES - ok
MARSS/DEIMOS - ok
BUCK - working fine – first flight
UHSAS - not working
VACC - ok
PAN - working well
SAW - working
UHSAS - not working, return to DMT
Satcom C - emails ok but position reports not getting through BADC to web, sorted half way through flight.

Aft core console - video display U/S

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

~3

MPDS

Not used

Satcom-H Calls

4 calls (one pos report) possible serviceability problem with forward handset.

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 17/10/18

Flight No: B 407

Pre-Flighter: Grafton

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Core chem operation
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	done already
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	Not carried
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	} left to rack operator
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	Documents, clean
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	pot p/len, 1/10 lower probe - cover left for operator removal.
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol** } left for core chem
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more	
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

B407 aoa at 500ft

B407 temps & dew point

B407 uvw at 500ft

B407 Neph return transit

B407 tephi 2

B407 tephi Prof 2

B407 tephi Prof 1

B407 tephi Prof 8

B407 final climb teph

B407 Nevzorov and JW 1

B407 Nevzorov and JW 2

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B407:

Log	Reason
Instrument Status	may not be correct – Flight Manager asked to check
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log. PSAP pump/filter info may be included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	No log available? Jamie T operated but not req to be flown according to Simon O
CVI	No log available?
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
CAPS / 2D-S	CAPS / 2D-S operator does not create a log sheet
AMS / SP2 log	AMS / SP2 operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

No Digital video avi recordings exist for this flight.

No Digital8 video recordings exist for this flight.